

JMEE**Journal of Marketing
Emerging Economies****| e-ISSN: 2792-4009 | www.openaccessjournals.eu | Vol. 10(1)****The Role of Marketing Policy in the Development of the United Arab Emirates and its Contrast with Iraq's Marketing Policy: A Comparative Analysis****Yao Jinfang**

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Abstract

This study compared Iraq and UAE marketing practices. This study used interviews about the topic. Marketing improves a nation's economy, as explained by marketing attracts capital and boosts competition. The study questioned UAE leaders to understand their policies. Marketing and PR executives and lawyers interviews support the concept that the UAE's marketing program has improved the reputation. Branding, investment incentives, and tourism promotion have improved the reputation. Interviews indicate various obstacles to Iraq's marketing plan struggled to use marketing for development due to resource limits, political disorganized marketing infrastructure. Given the outcomes, Iraq must price reform. Marketing infrastructure, public-private partnerships, and competition achieve this. These strategies may increase Iraq's competitiveness and attract investment. This study comparing the UAE and Iraq's marketing practices concluded that...